

Review

Research Progress on Quality Optimization of Fresh Wet Rice Noodles

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Abstract

As a traditional fermented rice product in China, fresh wet rice noodles (FWRN) suffer from an extremely short shelf life and susceptibility to spoilage due to their high moisture content (>60%). Furthermore, the industry faces urgent demands for upgrading due to severe product homogenization and low added value. This paper systematically reviews the quality evaluation systems and deterioration mechanisms of FWRN, with a focus on research progress in the screening and optimization of fermentation strains, regulation of process parameters, mechanisms of quality improvement, and preservation technologies. Studies indicate that Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) fermentation can improve the texture and cooking quality of rice noodles by altering starch molecular structures, degrading proteins and lipids, and producing exopolysaccharides. Additionally, the application of hurdle technology, complex preservatives, and novel physical preservation techniques can effectively extend the product's shelf life. Addressing current challenges such as the limited functionality of strains, unclear synergy mechanisms between quality and preservation, and lagging industrial application, this paper proposes future research directions including the directed breeding of functional strains, multi-omics analysis of quality mechanisms, and the development of clean-label preservation technologies. This review aims to provide a theoretical reference for the high-quality development of the FWRN industry.

Keywords: Fresh Wet Rice Noodles; Lactic Acid Bacteria Fermentation; Quality Optimization; Preservation Technology; Shelf-Life Extension

1. Introduction

Fresh wet rice noodles, a representative traditional fermented food in China, are primarily made from rice and indica rice. The production process involves cleaning, soaking, grinding, slurry preparation, gelatinization, shaping, and cooling, resulting in two main product forms: flat rice noodles (hefen) and round rice noodles. However, the rapid development of this industry has been accompanied by significant challenges, including potential quality and safety hazards, short shelf life, low added value, and imperfect production standards [1]. Specifically, four critical issues require urgent attention. First, there are substantial quality and safety risks. Historical data from regulatory inspections reveal frequent non-compliance regarding microbial counts and heavy metal levels, posing serious threats to consumer health [2]. Second, the product shelf life is extremely short. Due to a high moisture content of 60%–80%, fresh wet rice noodles typically last no more than 24–48 hours at room temperature, which severely restricts their distribution radius

and logistics efficiency [3]. Third, the added value of products remains low. The industry is trapped in a structural dilemma characterized by severe homogenization and razor-thin profit margins, lacking differentiated competitive advantages. Fourth, the standardization of production processes is low. Many operations remain in a "small workshop" mode, plagued by outdated equipment, poor sanitary conditions, and unstable product quality [4].

Consequently, developing green and efficient preservation technologies and optimizing fermentation processes to enhance product quality have become key pathways for the sustainable development of the fresh wet rice noodle industry. In recent years, scholars worldwide have conducted extensive research on fermentation strain screening, process parameter optimization, quality regulation mechanisms, and preservation technologies; however, systematic reviews remain scarce. This paper aims to review the status of research on quality optimization of fresh wet rice noodles, analyze existing problems, and propose future development directions, thereby providing a reference for technological upgrading in the industry.

2. Quality Evaluation System of Fresh Wet Rice Noodles

The quality evaluation of fresh wet rice noodles is a multidimensional and systematic endeavor. Constructing a scientific and rigorous evaluation system is crucial for guiding production practices, ensuring food safety, and meeting market demands. This system typically consists of three core components: sensory and texture evaluation oriented towards consumer experience; hygiene and stability assessment concerning product safety and shelf life; and raw material characteristic correlation evaluation. These three aspects are interrelated and complementary, jointly forming a whole-chain quality assurance framework ranging from raw material selection and process optimization to finished product quality control. Establishing and perfecting this evaluation system not only objectively quantifies product quality and guides enterprises in precisely regulating production processes but also effectively identifies and controls potential quality risks. Consequently, this enhances the product's market competitiveness and ensures that consumers obtain a safe, delicious, and consistent food experience. Specifically, the quality of fresh wet rice noodles is systematically judged primarily through the following major categories of indicators.

2.1 Core Quality Indicators and Evaluation Methods

2.1.1 Core Quality Evaluation Indicators

A) Sensory Characteristics

The sensory quality of rice noodles significantly influences consumer acceptance and serves as a primary criterion for judging their quality. Existing research indicates that sensory evaluation mainly encompasses the following aspects: regarding color, the noodles should retain the natural hue of rice, appearing uniformly white with good translucency. The odor should exhibit a pure and rich rice aroma, free from any off-flavors. Organoleptic properties primarily concern the physical integrity of the noodle strands; they are required to have a smooth surface without stickiness, a regular shape, and a low breakage rate. As for mouthfeel, this is a key indicator in sensory evaluation. The ideal texture should be soft, smooth, moderately elastic, and have appropriate viscosity, avoiding negative traits such as stickiness, undercooking, or roughness. Related studies have demonstrated that mouthfeel indicators have a significant impact on the overall sensory score [5].

B) Texture Characteristics

The texture analyzer serves as the primary tool for quality evaluation, utilizing objective and reproducible measurements to transform sensory experiences into quantitative indicators. Hardness of rice noodles indicates their resistance to deformation, a characteristic that affects the force perception during chewing; moderate hardness is the main factor contributing to the al dente texture. Hardness values show significant correlation with sensory evaluation results, with excessively high or low values adversely affecting product quality [6]. The elasticity index reflects the recovery ability of rice noodles after deformation, serving as the primary parameter for measuring springiness and smoothness; a significant positive correlation exists between elasticity index and overall sensory scores [7]. The chewiness parameter integrates hardness, elasticity, and cohesiveness characteristics to simulate the energy required for food from chewing to swallowing, and can be regarded as a comprehensive indicator for overall mouthfeel evaluation. Tensile testing utilizes parameters such as maximum tensile force and elongation distance to assess the flexibility and gluten strength characteristics of rice noodles, which are closely related to the non-breaking experience during consumption.

C) Cooking Characteristics

The cooking characteristics of rice noodles serve as a key metric for evaluating their edible quality [8]. Among these, the cooking breakage rate is a critical indicator; it represents the proportion of noodle strands breaking into lengths of less than 10 cm under specific cooking conditions. This value exhibits a significant negative correlation with the product's chewiness and cooking stability. The content of solids dissolved during the cooking process is termed cooking loss (or solids loss). The magnitude of this value reflects the compactness of the rice noodle's structure and significantly influences the smoothness of the final product. Furthermore, water absorption (or water uptake) is a parameter used to evaluate the degree of weight gain after cooking, which directly affects the fullness (plumpness) and textural quality of the final product.

2.1.2 Hygiene Safety and Storage Stability Indicators

In food safety evaluation models, microbial parameters such as total bacterial count, coliforms, and mold/yeast counts are used to measure product contamination and predict shelf life; these parameters have been established as basic safety thresholds by national standards such as GB 17400 [4]. With the extension of storage time, acidic substances produced by microbial activity cause the acidity value of rice noodles to rise continuously, a phenomenon that allows it to be used for monitoring changes in product freshness. Starch retrogradation alters the texture of fresh wet rice noodles, causing deterioration, primarily manifested as increased hardness and decreased mouthfeel. Iodine blue value determination can indirectly evaluate the degree of starch aging; an increase in this value usually indicates an increase in the dissolution of free starch, mainly due to reduced structural stability. Yang et al. [9] also utilized Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) to measure retrogradation enthalpy and combined it with X-ray diffraction to analyze changes in crystallinity, thereby quantifying the starch retrogradation process more precisely.

2.1.3 Raw Material and Component Correlation Indicators

The physicochemical characteristics of raw rice determine the quality of the finished rice noodles. Extensive research indicates that amylose content plays a crucial role in regulating the texture and cooking properties of fresh wet rice noodles, with a content exceeding 26% being preferable. This high amylose component strengthens the gel network structure, significantly improving the hardness, elasticity, and cooking stability of the rice noodles, while reducing breakage. In addition to amylose, studies have found that rice pasting properties, protein, endogenous lipids, and other components [10] are closely related to the texture characteristics of rice noodles.

2.2 Main Factors Affecting Quality Deterioration of Fresh Wet Rice Noodles

Fresh wet rice noodles undergo quality degradation during storage, manifesting in various complex ways, with microbial contamination and starch retrogradation being the primary forms of deterioration. Research results indicate that the initial microbial count of the product at the time of ex-factory release affects its shelf life [2]. Due to their high water activity and rich nutrient content, combined with variations in production environment cleanliness, these products are susceptible to contamination by microorganisms such as *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Lactobacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and coliforms during the cooling and packaging processes [11]. Under suitable environmental conditions, contaminating flora accelerate the spoilage process through rapid proliferation and metabolic activity. Therefore, using effective pretreatment sterilization techniques to control the initial microbial count is a primary technical method to ensure product shelf life. Moisture affects product quality deterioration; this environmental factor has a significant impact on product quality, and its activity level directly determines microbial proliferation potential. During storage, moisture undergoes dynamic migration and redistribution, significantly increasing the risk of microbial contamination. From a molecular perspective, moisture alters the aging state of starch, playing two roles in the starch aging process. Moisture acts as a plasticizer participating in the conformational rearrangement of starch molecular chains, while also affecting the formation rate of crystalline regions, thereby regulating the aging process. Analysis shows that starch retrogradation is most pronounced when moisture content is in the range of 30% to 60%. Although excessive moisture can inhibit starch retrogradation, it significantly increases microbial metabolic activity [12]. Thus, precise control of moisture parameters has become a key technical indicator for maintaining stable product shelf life.

Temperature is a critical environmental factor affecting product quality. Studies indicate that in high-temperature environments of 25 to 37°C, the reproduction rate of spoilage microorganisms accelerates,

causing acidity to rise and off-odors to develop, which is the main reason for the shortened shelf life of products stored at room temperature [13]. Temperature affects the starch aging process through complex mechanisms; in the low-temperature range of 2 to 4°C, starch molecules are prone to recrystallization, making the product texture hard and reducing elasticity, thereby accelerating quality deterioration. High-temperature environments can delay the aging process but are difficult to implement in actual production. Therefore, the main task of temperature control is to find the optimal balance point between microbial control and aging inhibition. Practical operations have found that refrigeration temperatures around 4°C can effectively inhibit microbial growth but accelerate aging reactions, while room temperature storage faces significant spoilage risks.

3 Current Status of Research on Quality Optimization of Fresh Wet Rice Noodles

3.1 Research on Screening and Optimization of Fermentation Strains

The quality and flavor of fermented fresh wet rice noodles mainly depend on the selected strains. Existing research has evolved from simple early analysis of microbial communities in natural fermentation liquids to the holistic screening, identification, functional evaluation, and genetic modification of dominant strains, aiming to develop specialized starters with reliable performance and unique flavors.

3.1.1 Screening of Dominant Strains

Multiple studies indicate that *Lactobacillus*, particularly *Lactobacillus plantarum*, plays a dominant role during natural fermentation and has a significant effect on improving the texture characteristics and flavor quality of rice noodles. Yi's team [14] screened the *L. plantarum* L.23 strain from natural fermentation liquid and conducted a comparative analysis. Results showed that this strain was more capable of enhancing mechanical indicators such as tensile strength, elasticity, and chewiness of fresh wet rice noodles compared to strains sourced from kimchi and sourdough. The optimal fermentation time reached 48 hours, and the resulting rice aroma flavor also exhibited distinct characteristics. Microorganisms such as *Lactobacillus fermentum* and *Acetobacter orientalis* have also been proven to impart unique flavor characteristics to fermented rice noodles; the former generates a rich fermented aroma, while the latter forms a special sour aroma, providing primary resources for developing diverse flavor products [15]. Regarding mixed-strain fermentation, Ren et al. [16] established a ternary fermentation model of *L. plantarum*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and *Lactobacillus casei*. Experimental results indicated that this model possesses strong acid-producing capabilities and can generate abundant volatile flavor compounds, significantly improving the layering and complexity of rice noodle flavor.

3.1.2 Strain Optimization and Breeding

Modern breeding technologies, including genome shuffling, offer distinct advantages for the selection of efficient fermentation strains. The team of Xiong [17] selected *Pediococcus pentosaceus* R02 and *Bacillus subtilis* R112 as parent strains and, through multiple rounds of genome recombination, obtained the mutant strain G2175 with significantly increased protease and amylase activity. Based on the analysis, the recombinant strain after fermentation preparation showed significant decreases in protein and fat content in the rice flour, while amylose and reducing sugar contents markedly increased. Following these biochemical compositional changes, the texture properties of fresh wet rice noodles were improved, mainly manifested as increased hardness and chewiness, along with a decreased breakage rate. The analysis indicated that regulating the enzyme-producing characteristics of the directionally improved strain could modulate the chemical composition of the rice matrix and achieve precise optimization of the final product quality.

3.2 Research on Optimization of Fermentation Process Parameters

Process parameters during fermentation are crucial regulatory elements that determine microbial metabolic activity, affect substrate conversion efficiency, and influence product quality. In recent years, research focus has shifted from simple parameter optimization to a holistic analysis of the combined effects of temperature, pH, fermentation duration, and inoculation ratio. Microbial growth metabolism and product accumulation are mainly regulated by fermentation temperature and time. Experimental data shows that *Lactobacillus plantarum* maintains good activity in the temperature range of 25 to 40°C, but the optimal fermentation periods vary among different strains. Wang et al. [18] analyzed the fermentation of the STB19 strain at 25°C for 60 hours and found that the texture characteristics and cooking performance of the rice noodles improved significantly. Yi's team [14] discovered that with increasing fermentation time, the mechanical properties of

rice noodles first increased and then decreased, reaching maximum values at 48 hours. The tensile force of strain L.23 reached 51.31 ± 5.29 g at 48 hours, outperforming other time points. These results suggest that strain-specific biological characteristics should be fully considered when optimizing fermentation processes.

pH significantly regulates microbial community dynamics and metabolic activity during fermentation. Microbial metabolism produces organic acids, gradually lowering the environmental pH, and this acidic environment in turn modulates microbial population succession and metabolic pathway selection. Experimental results demonstrate that reducing pH below 4.0 can inhibit the proliferation of spoilage microorganisms such as *Bacillus* species, providing early biopreservation effects [19]. In actual production, organic acids such as lactic acid or acetic acid are often added to adjust the pH of soaking water and fermentation mash, controlling contamination by undesirable bacteria and extending product shelf life [4]. However, excessive organic acid addition may negatively affect product flavor; therefore, some researchers have proposed using combined systems such as sodium lactate and sodium acetate, or buffer systems like glucono- δ -lactone, to maintain antimicrobial effects while improving taste quality.

3.3 Research on Quality Control Technologies

The improvement of fresh wet rice noodle quality is closely linked to the fermentation process, which not only alters raw material components but also changes starch molecular conformation and gel network characteristics. Current research in this field has gradually shifted from macroscopic quality analysis to the analysis of microscopic molecular mechanisms.

3.3.1 Regulation of Raw Material Components and Chemical Modification

The chemical composition of raw materials is a primary factor affecting rice noodle quality. Xiao et al. [20] showed that indica rice varieties with high amylose content are most suitable for producing fresh wet rice noodles, primarily because amylose content exhibits a significant negative correlation with product hardness and breakage rate, and directly affects cooking loss rate. Excessive protein and fat in rice interfere with intermolecular interactions among starch molecules, resulting in loose gel structures. During production, methods such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* fermentation or alkaline protease hydrolysis are commonly employed to reduce these components [21], thereby optimizing the textural characteristics of the product. To address deficiencies in native starch properties, adding exogenous starch is a common solution. Cong et al. [22] incorporated 5% aged rice flour and 3% konjac starch into the formulation of Shaoyang fresh wet rice noodles, utilizing their specific polysaccharides and fermentation products to improve the texture and flavor quality of the product.

3.3.2 Regulation of Moisture Content and Distribution State

The quality characteristics of fresh wet rice noodles are closely related to their moisture content of 60% to 80%; this moisture exists not only in the macroscopic ratio but also in the microscopic distribution. Macroscopically, insufficient moisture content leads to incomplete gelatinization and easy breakage. However, excessive moisture softens the texture and increases the possibility of microbial contamination. The study by Chen's team [21] demonstrated that the solid-liquid ratio is closely related to the texture characteristics of rice noodles. As the water proportion increased, the hardness of rice noodles exhibited a non-linear trend of first decreasing and then increasing. In terms of microscopic structure, Zhang et al. [23] used Low-Field Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (LF-NMR) for analysis and found that fresh wet rice noodles undergo moisture redistribution during storage; the loss of free water causes the product surface to dry out and hardness to increase. Inhibiting moisture migration through microwave-assisted water bath sterilization technology and high-barrier packaging materials can maintain the storage stability of rice noodles.

3.3.3 Evolution Mechanism of Starch Structure During Fermentation

The quality of fresh wet rice noodles is closely related to the structural characteristics of starch. Fermentation serves as a crucial method for improving the quality of fresh wet rice noodles. This process triggers systematic evolution in starch molecular structure through microbial metabolic activities, thereby influencing the product's texture, digestibility, and shelf-life stability. In recent years, with the advancement of analytical technologies, researchers have elucidated the dynamic changes in starch structure at the molecular level during fermentation.

During fermentation, the synergistic action of amylases and organic acids produced by microorganisms leads to the degradation and reorganization of starch molecules. Studies have shown that fermentation by

Lactobacillus plantarum can significantly alter the fine structure of starch, characterized by a shortened average chain length and an increased proportion of A-chains (DP 6-12) and B1 short chains (DP 13-24), resulting in an optimized amylopectin structure. Zou et al. [24] systematically analyzed the chain length distribution characteristics of rice starch from different origins and found that when the A-chain proportion was 25.03%-30.90% and the B1-chain proportion was 47.82%-52.02%, the rheological behavior and textural properties of the starch gel differed significantly, with the short-chain proportion showing a positive correlation with gel hardness. This finding provides a theoretical basis for understanding the impact of starch chain rearrangement on noodle texture during fermentation.

Fermentation not only modifies starch structure but also reshapes the starch-protein interaction network through protein hydrolysis and exopolysaccharide (EPS) production. Wu et al. [25] found that acid production by lactic acid bacteria fermentation could activate endogenous enzymes, causing amylase activity in rice flour sourdough to first increase and then decrease, while protein hydrolytic activity increased, leading to the degradation of macromolecular soluble glutenin. This weakening of the protein network reduced the elastic modulus and viscous modulus of the dough, resulting in a softer noodle texture.

3.4 Research on Preservation Technologies

As a traditional staple food with high moisture and high starch content, fresh wet rice noodles are highly susceptible to microbial contamination and starch retrogradation-induced aging, resulting in an extremely short shelf life that severely restricts their industrial development. Currently, preservation technologies for fresh wet rice noodles have evolved from single chemical preservation toward integrated preservation systems based on multi-technology synergy.

In terms of chemical preservation, organic acids such as ascorbic acid and citric acid have been extensively studied due to their significant antibacterial effects and high safety profiles. Studies have shown that 90 mg/mL ascorbic acid and 120 mg/mL citric acid exhibit good inhibitory effects on the main spoilage bacteria of Guilin rice noodles, including *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Bacillus cereus* [26]. Among physical sterilization technologies, non-thermal processing methods such as microwave treatment, ultra-high pressure technology, and cold plasma have attracted attention for their ability to maintain product quality effectively. Gong et al. [27] reviewed the application of ultra-high pressure technology in rice product preservation, pointing out that this technology can effectively inactivate microorganisms while reducing thermosensitive nutrient losses. Zhang et al. [28] found that microwave treatment could improve the physicochemical properties of fresh wet wheat flour, thereby enhancing the quality of fresh wet noodles. Huang et al. [29] optimized the combination of hurdle factors, adopting pasteurization (90°C, 30 min) combined with lactic acid dipping (1.0%, 60 s), achieving a shelf life of 90 days for instant rice noodles.

Biological preservation has become a research hotspot due to its high safety and good consumer acceptance. Lactic acid bacteria fermentation technology exerts dual functions of bacteriostasis and anti-aging through the production of metabolites such as organic acids, bacteriocins, and exopolysaccharides. Nie et al. [30] found that sourdough fermented with nisin-producing *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis* could extend the shelf life of fresh noodles and improve their textural characteristics. In the field of fresh wet rice noodles, Hu et al. [31] systematically studied the inhibitory mechanism of ϵ -polylysine hydrochloride (ϵ -PLH) against *Salmonella typhimurium*, discovering that ϵ -PLH exerts antibacterial effects by disrupting cell membrane integrity, inducing oxidative stress, and disturbing energy metabolism, with an optimal concentration of 128 μ g/mL, demonstrating good preservation effects in wet rice noodles.

The application of rapid non-destructive detection technologies has provided new means for quality monitoring of fresh wet rice noodles. Low-field nuclear magnetic resonance (LF-NMR) technology can monitor water migration status and distribution proportions during storage in real time, and combined with the Avrami equation, can establish starch aging kinetic models to achieve shelf-life prediction [32]. Wang et al. [33] used LF-NMR to analyze the effect of lysine addition on water distribution in fermented semi-dried brown rice noodles, finding that lysine could increase bound water content by promoting specific intermolecular interactions among starch molecules, thereby improving gel water-holding capacity and textural properties. Near-infrared spectroscopy combined with chemometric methods also offers possibilities for rapid detection of main components and quality indicators of fresh wet rice noodles.

In summary, future preservation technologies for fresh wet rice noodles will develop toward "green,

intelligent, and synergistic" directions. Through the organic integration of chemical, physical, and biological technologies, combined with standardized production processes and automated equipment, a comprehensive preservation system will be constructed to meet consumer demands for food safety and quality.

4. Conclusion and Future Perspectives

As a significant representative of traditional staple foods in southern China, fresh wet rice noodles have seen their quality optimization and preservation research evolve from macroscopic, empirical improvements to microscopic, molecular-level mechanism regulation. This review indicates that the quality of fresh wet rice noodles is influenced by the interaction of multiple factors, with microbial contamination and starch retrogradation being the core bottlenecks leading to short shelf life and quality deterioration. In terms of quality optimization, significant improvements in texture and flavor have been achieved by screening superior fermentation strains (such as *Lactobacillus plantarum*), optimizing fermentation parameters (temperature, pH, time), and regulating raw material ratios (high amylose content, addition of functional supplements). Specifically, research into fermentation mechanisms has revealed the filling and plasticizing effects of microbial metabolites (e.g., exopolysaccharides) on the starch network structure, providing a theoretical basis for endogenous anti-retrogradation. Regarding preservation, single hurdle technologies often fail to meet the demands for long-term preservation. Consequently, the synergistic combination of biological preservation (e.g., ϵ -polylysine), physical sterilization (e.g., microwave-assisted water bath), and precise temperature-controlled packaging (low-temperature refrigeration, high-barrier materials) has become an effective strategy for extending shelf life.

Looking forward, the technological upgrading of the fresh wet rice noodle industry should focus on the following directions: First, constructing intelligent quality prediction models. Combining rapid non-destructive detection technologies such as low-field nuclear magnetic resonance and near-infrared spectroscopy to monitor water migration and starch retrogradation status in real time, establishing shelf life prediction models, and achieving the transformation from "empirical preservation" to "precise preservation." Second, developing green and efficient composite preservation systems. Deeply exploring the synergistic antibacterial mechanisms of natural antimicrobial peptides and probiotics to replace or reduce the use of chemical preservatives, meeting consumers' demand for clean labels. Third, promoting the standardization and automation of process equipment. Addressing the significant hygiene risks of small workshop-style production, promoting standardized clean operation area designs and automated packaging lines to control microbial contamination risks from the source. Fourth, deeply investigating the microbial community mysteries of traditional fermentation. Utilizing metagenomics and metabolomics technologies to analyze the succession patterns of microbial communities during natural fermentation and their coupling mechanisms with flavor substance formation, directionally cultivating functional starters with regional characteristics to enhance product added value.

In summary, through interdisciplinary integration and collaborative innovation across the industrial chain, the fresh wet rice noodle industry is expected to break through the dual constraints of "short shelf life" and "low quality," achieving the transformation from traditional workshop food to high-quality, standardized modern food while ensuring food safety.

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